

Yoga For Health And Wellness

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Abstract:

Health is not a mere absence of disease. It is a dynamic expression of life in terms of how joyful, loving and enthusiastic. Yoga is an integral part of our lifestyle. It removes the impurities from the level of mind and unites everything with the spirit. Yogis in The Himalayas can survive without food because they don't need to eat as their body survives on prana. But we need to eat and maintain a healthy diet. Vihaar (Daily Routine) plays a tremendous role in measuring how healthy an individual is. A sadhak should know what is suitable for his/ her living. Some advanced yoga poses may look intimidating, many are suitable for beginners. Yoga is a form of physical activity, and regularly practicing yoga can help people meet the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recommendation of 150 minutes of exercise per week. This helps people live a healthy lifestyle and maintain a moderate weight. Yoga is an accessible form of exercise that benefits physical and mental health. Most people are able to start with beginner yoga poses from the comfort of their own home.

Keywords: Yoga, Health and Wellness

Introduction:

Health is not a mere absence of disease. It is a dynamic expression of life – in terms of how joyful, loving and enthusiastic you are - Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar

One who is stable and established in the self is healthy. That is to say that identifying a healthy person doesn't only entail physical fitness, but what's even more crucial is ones mental fitness. One cannot say that 'I'm healthy, but not interested in life'. The enthusiasm in life shows how healthy you are.

Causes of sickness or ill health are generally noted as impurities on the level of mind, body and speech. Your own speech can create distress in you as well as other people around you. Even distress or discomfort should be treated as an illness.

Body, mind and spirit are like a tripod – even if one aspect isn't functioning properly, our

life will not be balanced and that will lead to ill health. Yoga (a component of ayurveda) is that link which creates a harmony by aligning all the three components (body, mind and spirit) into one. This harmony, in turn exists to support life.

Yoga is an integral part of our lifestyle. It removes the impurities from the level of mind and unites everything with the spirit. For instance, insomnia could be connected to stress, anxiety or depression. You have to address that issue instead of merely taking medication. This way, you have a wider perception of your own mind, body, thoughts and emotions and there's more clarity and you are able to guide your prana (life force) in a positive way to progress in life.

One can start practicing Yoga at any given moment of time and you may start with meditation or directly with pranayama without even doing the asanas (postures). Make sure that when you practice yoga asanas, you don't just

stretch the body because the mind has to be with the body. You can't be watching television or reading the newspaper because if your awareness isn't there, the asanas won't have much effect on you. But if each stretch is synchronized with the breath and awareness, your practice will become a yogic practice.

Role Of Food in Keeping One Healthy:

Yogis in The Himalayas can survive without food because they don't need to eat as their body survives on prana. But we need to eat and maintain a healthy diet.

Did you know that your next day starts from your dinner? What you eat, what time you eat and how much you eat affects your sleep, the morning and your entire day.

Needless to say, ahaar (food) makes a profound impact on your body and mind. Imbalance of vata, pitta and kapha (three prime energies in the body) lead to most health-related issues. For instance, if someone's pitta (fire element) is high, certain foods can aggravate the pitta and cause restlessness, lack of sleep and anxiety, which makes it a necessity to know what foods are suitable for the body and mind by consulting an ayurvedic doctor.

Second Most Important Aspect of Health:

Vihaar (Daily Routine) plays a tremendous role in measuring how healthy an individual is. A sadhak should know what is suitable for his/ her living.

There is a tendency in our body towards health. At one level, our body intelligence signals that what we are doing is not alright, but we all have our excuses because we are following our mind and emotion. That intelligence fails when you become a slave to your mind and creates problems on a physical level. And soon, it becomes a pattern.

A headache is not a disease, but a signal for something bigger, and when we suppress that sign with painkillers, the real cause soon surfaces on a much bigger scale.

How Does Yoga Affect The Body, And How Can Someone Start Practicing Yoga?

Yoga is a physical and spiritual practice originating in India. It is accessible to beginners, and most people can reap the health benefits of regularly practicing yoga.

Yoga poses focus on developing a connection between the body and the breath. In addition to reducing stress levels, consistent yoga practice can improve a person's flexibility, strength, and balance.

Although some advanced yoga poses may look intimidating, many are suitable for beginners. Most people can start practicing yoga.

Can Yoga Help With Weight Management?

Yoga is a form of physical activity, and regularly practicing yoga can help people meet the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [Trusted Source](#) recommendation of 150 minutes of exercise per week. This helps people live a healthy lifestyle and maintain a moderate weight.

Yoga exercises are beneficial for weight loss. It examined 50 adults with obesity and assigned them to either Hatha (slower pace) or Vinyasa (faster pace) yoga practices. Although both groups of individuals lost weight after 6 months, the program also included a calorie- and fat-restricted diet, which likely contributed to the weight loss.

The results of this study suggest that people who would like to practice yoga as part of a weight management program should choose the type and duration that suits them best.

Other Benefits of Yoga:

When people practice yoga frequently, they may notice their health improving in other ways. These can include:

Quitting smoking:

Stress is a significant barrier for those trying to quit smoking. Because yoga exercises can reduce stress and improve mood, the practice could benefit people who may be finding it difficult to stop smoking.

People who smoked to an 8-week program of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and either yoga or wellness classes. The results showed that those who practiced yoga twice a week were more likely to stop smoking than those who attended the wellness classes. This outcome was particularly common among people who smoked lightly.

Menopause:

Yoga may improve psychological symptoms and fatigue symptoms in menopausal individuals. However, there is no evidence to suggest that yoga exercises can improve physical symptoms, such as muscle pain, or vasomotor symptoms, such as hot flashes and night sweats.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD):

COPD causes respiratory muscle weakness, which can make it hard to breathe. Because yoga may improve lung function, researchers wanted to know if it could improve inspiratory muscle performance.

Veterans with severe or very severe COPD experienced improvements in muscle performance after completing a 6-week yoga program. These results suggest yoga is a promising tool for improving outcomes in people with COPD. However, more research is needed to understand how a wider demographic of people with COPD respond to yoga as part of a treatment plan.

Summary:

Yoga is an accessible form of exercise that benefits physical and mental health. Most people are able to start with beginner yoga poses from the comfort of their own home. In addition to improving flexibility, strength, and balance, yoga can also reduce stress levels and aid in weight management.

References:

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